

T. O. Grafova, Y. A. Medvedkina, A. A. Vasil'tsov

Development of Antitrust Compliance in the Internal Control System for Cross-Border E-Commerce

KEYWORDS

digital platforms,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of this study stems from the growth of international e-commerce, the tightening of antitrust requirements, and the need for companies to promptly adapt their internal control systems to comply with laws across different countries, prevent violations, and minimize the risk of fines and reputational losses.

Materials and methods. Legislative and regulatory acts, articles from international scientific journals, conference abstracts, and official data from research companies were used as study materials. The analysis of the e-commerce markets in China, the USA, and the Russian Federation was based on annual sales growth data and a growth test, using linear regression with the coefficient of determination to identify trends.

Results. We analyzed the features and limitations of the regulation of digital platform markets in Russia through the prism of foreign experience in the USA, EU, and China, which allowed us to identify regulatory problems in Russian legislative practice as a factor reducing the effectiveness of antitrust compliance in the corporate governance system of electronic trading platforms in Russia. The possibilities and directions for the development of internal compliance within the internal control system of Russian marketplaces are substantiated, the sustainable development of which will require a revision of the business model, operational conditions, and contractual frameworks for interactions with sellers. The importance of adjusting platform economic policies and establishing an internal compliance system to prevent reputational and financial losses for marketplaces and sellers is emphasized.

Conclusion. Restrictions on sellers' interactions with buyers increase the risk of reputational losses. In the context of the ESG agenda, the emphasis is on socially oriented business transformation and balancing contracts among the platform, sellers, and buyers. To effectively regulate digital markets, it is necessary to revise marketplace business models and legislation to strengthen antitrust compliance and ensure sustainable development that prioritizes social and corporate governance considerations.

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INTRODUCTION

The study's relevance stems from the growing volume of cross-border e-commerce, and the increase in international transactions requires more effective control and compliance mechanisms.

Regulators around the world are introducing new regulations to prevent monopolistic behavior and protect competition in the online environment. Cross-border trade is often associated with complex legal regimes, which heightens the need for implementing adapted internal controls. In the context of globalization, companies must comply with regulations across different countries, making the study of antitrust compliance development essential.

The development of the global economy in the last decade is characterized by the accumulation of structural contradictions, one of which is the digitalization of worldwide business and the associated risks of market power redistribution in the digital segment of international trade.

The institutional imbalance emerging in global trade and its accelerated monopolization require changes in the regulatory environment, as well as the introduction of new corporate governance practices that consider the global ESG agenda for business transformation and the need to increase sustainability.

Reliability and sustainability criteria are increasingly shaping the modern restructuring of corporate governance systems, reflecting companies' overall policies.

The most significant difficulties in implementing such policies today are associated with trading platforms, which are actively expanding their monopoly power and increasing pressure on business trading partners within platform ecosystems.

In this article, we examine this issue through the prism of increasing the effectiveness of compliance control practices focused on implementing strategic guidelines for the development of marketplaces and ecosystems without exacerbating market asymmetry in the digital commodity circulation segment.

To update and substantiate the specifics of the required restructuring of corporate governance systems and platform policies for compliance implementation, we consider two main problematic aspects of their functioning (using the example of Russia):

- weak regulation of Internet commerce, with institutional restrictions preventing monopolization being practically absent in the Trade Act;

- the trade policies of the platforms themselves, which increase market pressure on partners both from the supply side (sellers) and the demand side (end consumers).

Purpose of the study: analysis of the development of antitrust compliance in the internal control system of cross-border e-commerce.

Research objectives:

1. Analyze the features and limitations of the regulation of digital platform markets (on the example of Russia) through the prism of foreign experience in the USA, EU, and China.
2. Identify regulatory problems in Russian legislative practice as factors reducing the effectiveness of antitrust compliance in the corporate governance system of electronic trading platforms in Russia.
3. Justify the possibilities and directions for the development of internal compliance in the internal control system of domestic marketplaces, the sustainable development of which requires revision of business models, operational conditions, and contractual frameworks for interactions with sellers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study materials comprised legislative and regulatory acts, in particular federal laws and regulations on competition and antitrust (the Federal Law on Protection of Competition in Russia, EU antitrust directives, US competition laws).

Also included were articles from peer-reviewed international scientific journals: *E-Commerce Review*, *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems: Applications in Engineering and Technology*, *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, *International Journal of Information Management*, etc.; abstracts from international conferences: *2020 International Conference on Big Data Economy and Information Management*, *Actual Problems of Private International Law. Collection of Articles of the II International Interdisciplinary Scientific and Practical Congress, Transport: Science, Education, Production. Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference*, as well as official data from research companies.

To analyze the e-commerce markets in China, the USA, and the Russian Federation, data on annual sales growth and annual growth tests were used. Direct

linear regression was employed as the trend line method, with the coefficient of determination serving to identify trends.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The main logistical challenges of cross-border e-commerce include the complexity of shipping and customs clearance, delays, high transportation costs, the lack of a unified cargo regulation and tracking system, and the risk of goods being damaged or lost.

T. Liu reviews the current state of transnational e-commerce logistics and research on logistics risk. After comparing the advantages and disadvantages of various risk assessment methods, neural networks and genetic algorithms were chosen as primary methods. The author developed a system of indices to assess the logistics risks of cross-border e-commerce [1].

M. Giuffrida et al. note that due to its rapid growth, cross-border e-commerce (CBEC) is becoming a popular model of internationalization, especially in Chinese markets. The authors analyze logistical uncertainties and risks in this area. According to them, the risk management strategies adopted depend on the type of logistical uncertainty faced by companies and, to a lesser extent, on the industry in which they operate [2].

A. Liu et al. reviewed the current state of cross-border e-commerce in China and factors influencing its development to identify gaps in the literature. Cross-border e-commerce in China shows steady progress, although several problems remain: low efficiency in customs clearance, complex monitoring and supervision, issues with tax benefit settlement, payment risks, etc. [3].

R. Liu observes that SMEs face difficulties in risk resilience, product uniformity, and financing. The volatile international situation, cross-border payment risks, and high cross-border logistics costs have also hampered CBEC development. The author proposes a general strategy for developing cross-border e-commerce for SMEs through favorable government policies and the application of big data technologies [4].

Consumers perceive risks such as lack of information, delays, loss of goods, return problems, and payment security issues, which can affect trust and willingness to shop in cross-border e-commerce.

H. Jiang et al. examine factors influencing consumers' platform choices and the relationships among these factors. According to the study, the most significant elements for consumers choosing a cross-border import e-commerce platform are products and experience, while services and risks are practical factors, with risks having the most critical impact [5].

Dan Ma et al. note that uncertainties in cross-border online shopping, particularly physical remoteness and lack of trust, affect consumer decision-making. Perceived risk negatively impacts purchase intentions, behavior, and platform recommendations [6].

Huang Yuwen et al. write that trust perception is the primary mechanism for establishing trust in cross-border e-commerce. Researchers analyze consumer characteristics to build a system of consumer-perception confidence indices [7].

Y. Ma et al., for sustainability research, state that intentions to make a cross-border online purchase offer a framework of variables influencing continued cross-border purchases, mediated by customer satisfaction. Among the proposed independent variables, electronic feedback, website design quality, and the trust and uncertainty avoidance index significantly predict customer satisfaction [8].

Legal issues include customs regulations, consumer protection, intellectual property, taxation, data security, and the enforcement of contracts across different countries.

M. Guo notes that China's cross-border e-commerce sector faces risks of intellectual property infringement. According to the researcher, it is necessary to improve relevant laws and regulations, the mechanisms for supervising export products, and the definitions of liability for violations of intellectual property rights across countries [9].

According to Li Fang, the legal risks of intellectual property infringement in cross-border e-commerce have become a key factor limiting its further growth. Scientists propose countermeasures, including improving the legal system of intellectual property rights in cross-border e-commerce and clarifying relevant laws and regulations; creating and enhancing a mechanism for access and supervision of cross-border e-commerce enterprises, etc. [10], and strengthening the assessment and supervision of the creditworthiness of enterprises [11].

Zhang Jinyuan notes that a constant aggravation of trade disputes and conflicts accompanies the development of cross-border e-commerce. Violations of

intellectual property rights in cross-border e-commerce, according to the author, are widespread. The researcher proposed countermeasures at three levels: firstly, companies engaged in cross-border electronic commerce should actively protect their intellectual property rights and promote their core values; second, the government should strengthen the system of public services in the field of intellectual property to help companies cope with legal risks; and finally, industry associations should enhance their supervisory and coordinating functions [12].

Risk mitigation strategies in cross-border trade include applying insurance policies, conducting thorough partner analysis, introducing modern tracking technologies, complying with legal requirements, and using transparent transaction terms.

Shuzhong Ma et al. believe that the cross-border e-commerce industry today faces serious management risks spanning national borders. Researchers are studying the impact of different risk mitigation strategies on the market performance of international online merchants and their benefits for consumers [13].

Bo Song et al. write that existing regulations from different countries could pose a significant risk to cross-border e-commerce (CBEC). The authors propose a risk assessment method based on text mining to quantitatively measure the risk associated with CBEC commodities. The results show that the proposed method improves CBEC commodity risk assessment by increasing both its efficiency and accuracy [14].

L. Zhou et al. examine the supply chain risk factors in cross-border B2C e-commerce and propose strategies to mitigate them. Researchers show that, from the enterprise's perspective, internal resilience to risks is more important than maintaining capital stability and creating an effective mechanism for monitoring and managing risks. From the enterprise's perspective, external risk intensity should be avoided in two key areas: transaction security and logistics [15].

J. Li et al. propose an analysis-based textual framework to study consumer risk perceptions in One Belt and One Road countries based on a collection of online textual feedback. The authors identified six main risk factors and reported consumers' perceptions of risk in nine countries of the OBOR initiative [16].

Cross-border e-commerce reform significantly reduces supply chain risks for Chinese businesses, according to B. Dai and S. Min. The creation of pilot cross-border e-commerce zones primarily reduces supply chain risks for non-state enterprises located in coastal areas and for enterprises with established digital infrastructure. Cross-border e-commerce reform improves investment efficiency and reduces the risk of stock price collapse by mitigating supply chain risks [17].

Junli Lyu shows that the creation of pilot zones of cross-border e-commerce in China significantly stimulates growth in the consumption of tourist goods by urban residents [18].

Yi Jing and Peng Yang note that there are differences in logistical laws and cultural practices across countries and regions. Researchers formulate targeted countermeasures, in combination with big data technologies, to identify risks and propose practical, feasible solutions, including preventive measures, for cross-border e-commerce export risks in China [19].

S. Du et al. believe that the Belt and Road Initiative has significantly contributed to the growth of cross-border e-commerce over the past few years. According to scientists, SME effectiveness is primarily determined by customer satisfaction in a customer-oriented market. The researchers proposed a method to more accurately calculate the relationship strength between each risk factor, accounting for the impact of consumer requirements, thereby enabling risk prioritization for small and medium-sized enterprises engaged in cross-border e-commerce [20].

X. Xu and S. Zhou proposed a cross-border supply chain decision model with four different risk preference combinations. The relationship between the risk preference ratio and the ordering strategy for a foreign warehouse, and between the risk preference ratio and the pricing strategy for a cross-border platform, is analyzed using numerical examples [21].

Wang Lei and Gao Xuezheng write that the specifics of cross-border e-commerce transactions and an imperfect tax mechanism increase the risk of financial management. The authors developed a model for analyzing financial risks using support vector machines (SVMs) and fuzzy number analysis. Using this model, the accuracy of forecasting investment risk and operational risk reached 80%. When forecasting financial and tax risk, accuracy increased by 12.4% [22].

Hong Su examines the characteristics, existing challenges, and countermeasures to streamline the operations and risk management of cross-border e-commerce platforms. Scientists propose several measures: improving the efficiency of logistics and supply chain management; improving payment and currency exchange systems; strengthening information security and privacy protection mechanisms, etc. [23].

For the sustainable development of cross-border e-commerce, it is necessary to implement environmentally friendly logistics solutions, improve transaction transparency and security, develop local markets, support ethical business practices, and stimulate the adoption of sustainable technologies.

X. Liu et al. consider factors affecting the sustainability of the cross-border e-commerce supply chain. Scientists suggest making supply chain adaptability a top priority, which can be achieved by strengthening a culture of risk management, fostering collaboration between partners, and increasing supply chain flexibility [24].

Yang Yan analyzes the challenges of expanding cross-border e-commerce at three levels: trademark registration strategy, appropriate use and monitoring mechanisms, and dispute resolution and system improvement. The author believes that, thanks to a systematic registration scheme, continuous monitoring, and the comprehensive use of diversified rights protection methods, cross-border e-commerce enterprises can not only effectively reduce legal risks but also enhance the stability of their brands in the international market [25].

According to P. He et al. e-commerce supply chain management has been a reasonably popular research topic in recent decades. Analysis of the joint occurrence of keywords allowed the authors to identify seven main subject clusters. Research gap analysis indicates that future research may combine streaming, new technologies, disruption risk, and behavioral preferences in e-commerce supply chain management research [26].

A review of sources showed that many researchers note the need to improve laws, oversight mechanisms, and the coordination of responsibilities across countries. Legal risks limit the industry's development and require improving the legal system, increasing control over enterprises, and protecting their rights. The aggravation of trade disputes is associated with the prevalence of violations, which require active intervention by companies, strengthened public services, and the participation of industry associations in protecting intellectual property.

Research shows that the cross-border e-commerce industry faces multiple management and operational risks related to international regulations, logistics, finance, and consumer perceptions. Risk assessment methods are proposed using mining and modeling, as well as strategies to ensure supply chains, strengthen regulatory mechanisms, and enhance information security.

RESULTS

E-commerce in China is experiencing unprecedented growth, with the market size projected to reach 19.6 trillion yuan (approximately USD 3 trillion) by 2024, corresponding to a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 12.4%. Compared

to the 2021 estimate of 13.8 trillion yuan (about USD 2.1 trillion), these indicators reflect the sector's significant dynamics and underscore China's growing role in the global digital economy. The main factors driving this industry's development are the growth of Internet users, the introduction of mobile technologies, and changing consumer preferences.

The market size is expected to reach USD 2.4 trillion by 2025. Among the leading participants in the sector are large corporations Alibaba and JD.com, which hold dominant positions. E-commerce volume in China has shown steady growth from 2017 to 2025, with the current market valuation of about USD 1.13 trillion, making it the largest in the world and accounting for approximately 50% of global e-commerce transactions.

Forecasts indicate continued positive momentum, with a CAGR of around 12.42% between 2023 and 2027, leading to a market size of around USD 2.375 trillion by the end of this period (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 China E-commerce Value in 2017-2025

The United States accounts for approximately 19% of global e-commerce sales, meaning that out of every USD 100 spent on e-commerce worldwide, USD 19 is spent in the United States [27]. US e-commerce sales in 2024 are estimated at USD 1.19 trillion and are projected to reach USD 1.29 trillion by the end of the year, reflecting an 8.2% year-on-year increase (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 Annual US e-commerce sales growth

The e-commerce market peaked in 2020 (see Figure 3). Projected growth from 2024 to 2029 shows a CAGR of approximately 9%, indicating steady increases in consumer spending within the e-commerce segment.

Figure 3 Annual growth rate of US e-sales

The main areas of consumer spending are machinery, clothing, and food. By 2025, e-commerce sales in the United States are projected to reach USD 1.29 trillion, representing approximately 9% growth. These figures underscore the high level of development and significance of the e-commerce market in the American economy.

The rapid expansion of marketplaces in Russia has resulted in their share exceeding half of the total online trading volume (RUB 7.7 trillion; see Figure 4), reaching 78% in 2023, up from 69% in 2022 and 58% in 2021 [28, p. 4].

Figure 4 Dynamics of e-commerce development in Russia in 2020-2023 [29, p. 3]

In the context of such expansion, the extremely weak regulation of the digital segment provides sites with virtually unlimited opportunities to modify operating conditions, creating excessive risks of price manipulation, imposing unfavorable and discriminatory terms for sellers and heightening social tension (see Table 1).

Table 1

Shortcomings of the system for developing regulatory rules for competition
and regulating digital markets in Russia

Shortcoming	Risk and its consequences
Fragmentary regulation of Internet commerce	Excessive risks of price manipulation, imposition of unfavorable and discriminatory conditions for platform sellers, and an increase in social tension due to weak protection of the rights of platform users (sellers and buyers). The underdeveloped legislative framework for digital trade undermines the effectiveness of antitrust compliance within corporate governance systems of platforms.
Failure to elaborate on individual standards	Individual legislative initiatives at the project stage may contradict existing laws, such as consumer protection regulations, increasing the likelihood of litigation and lawsuits, as well as the potential expansion of various abuses.
Deregulation of Platform-User Relationships	Contractual models and terms of interaction between marketplaces and businesses are insufficiently regulated, which increases reputational and financial risks for both parties.
Lack of criteria for assessing market boundaries, etc.	Ambiguous definitions of competitive objects when determining digital market boundaries and identifying violations of antitrust prohibitions by digital platforms. There is a lack of standard, unified criteria for evaluating market boundaries for digital platforms.
Low effect of regulatory measures	The prevalence of a retrospective (ex post) approach in measures and regulations for violations, particularly antitrust laws, rather than preventive (ex ante) approaches, reduces the effectiveness of timely identification and mitigation of antitrust risks in digital markets. This also weakens incentives to refrain from anticompetitive actions.

The norms proposed by the Parliament of the Russian Federation are often poorly studied and, in some cases, contradict existing legislation. An example of such norms is the prohibition on marketers charging buyers for the return of goods, which conflicts with consumer protection law, granting sellers, for instance, the right to recover delivery costs.

Within the framework of another bill initiated by parliamentarians, the cost of all services provided by marketplaces to partners cannot exceed 10% of the total cost of the goods they sell. The explanatory note to such a draft lacks a clear business rationale for the proposed service cost thresholds. Another example is a proposal to prohibit sites from selling their own goods if the platforms' revenue exceeds 150 billion rubles.

The consequence of this superficial approach may be the loss of market and commercial incentives for aggregators to provide transportation, store products at platform warehouses, and promote them.

The general direction of parliamentarians' regulatory initiatives is appropriate, focusing on eliminating the main contradictions in e-commerce, addressing market monopolization, and mitigating the imbalances in market power caused by the growing asymmetry in negotiating positions between platforms and counterparties.

The evolution of antitrust regulation of digital platforms shows that many countries have accumulated extensive experience in this area, which cannot be unequivocally deemed successful. The USA, the European Union (which implements its supranational antitrust policy through the European Commission and develops pan-European approaches), and the antitrust practices of individual BRICS countries show that traditional antitrust instruments, which are largely retrospective (ex post), are insufficient for the timely identification and mitigation of antitrust risks in digital markets [30, p. 84-85].

The dynamics of digital markets necessitate the implementation of a preventive (ex ante) approach, including various mechanisms that limit large digital companies from gaining unfair market advantages for their own products and services (self-preferencing), a practice actively applied by the European Commission, for example, in the Google Shopping case (displaying their own services at the top of search results).

A review of global antitrust practices shows that, despite imposing heavy fines on digital giants, the measures are often delayed and fail to provide strong incentives to refrain from anti-competitive practices. The completion of the Google Shopping investigation and the resultant decisions and instructions proved ineffective in restoring competition [30, p. 85].

The lack of consistent US law enforcement since the early 2000s is notable. High-profile lawsuits against digital companies reflect the position of national authorities, which intentionally limited antitrust pressure on ecosystems to support their initial growth in global markets. The result of this liberal approach was a series of investigations into anti-competitive practices by digital giants (Alphabet (Google), Amazon, Facebook (Meta), and Apple), revealing numerous instances of unacceptable actions by large ecosystem companies, which required adjustments to US antitrust laws [31; 32].

Overall, the modern version of antitrust law remains underdeveloped worldwide, as evidenced by the dismissal of many claims against digital companies deemed insufficiently substantiated. This has allowed Amazon to further restrict third-party

sellers' ability to sell goods under favorable terms (the claim against the company was dismissed in March 2022 by a court in the District of Columbia, USA).

Chinese authorities adopted a stricter stance, limiting the unlimited expansion of Alipay and Tenpay and preventing monopolization of the digital segment of retail payments through a series of measures [33].

The challenge of developing regulatory rules for competition in digital markets is relevant to many countries with high levels of capital concentration in e-commerce segments (USA, EU, Brazil, India, and China) [34].

Regarding marketplaces, Germany's experience is noteworthy for Russia, as its regulations encompass a wide range of requirements for marketplace operations, which are directly enforceable without amendments to national legislation [35, p. 42-43]:

- Each marketplace must provide regulators with information on how a product or supplier is ranked on a virtual shelf and which supplier violations are subject to sanctions;
- Each marketplace must publicly announce proposed additional services or financial products and avoid mandatory imposition;
- The marketplace is obliged to refrain from retroactively changing conditions.

However, despite regulation in foreign markets, the problem of monopolization by trading platforms remains relevant, despite growing targeted intervention by authorities.

In Russia, the FAS review of anti-competitive practices by large digital companies (Yandex, Avito, Cyan, 2GIS, Tutu.ru, etc.) aims to prevent unfair competition and balance the interests of ecosystems and other businesses [36].

The complexity of digital ecosystem business models limits the application of multi-instrument approaches and direct administrative intervention, which is today partially replaced by the evolutionary priority of self-regulation by large platforms within a still insufficiently transparent and stable legal framework [37].

All of these factors constrain the effectiveness and broader application of antitrust compliance.

It is important to note that digital markets and sales scaling in e-commerce are complex, with intricate cost structures, and their cost-effectiveness remains relatively low. This highlights the specifics of marketplace evolution, the bulk of which, after decades, only achieves operational surplus.

Investment risks, fierce competition, the specifics of business models, and the expansion of niche market segments create a challenging nexus of interests, where marketplaces can easily exceed regulatory boundaries, which remain imprecisely defined [38].

In the context of aggressive growth, marketplaces are trying to increase value-added services by expanding paid options for sellers, whose offerings are becoming increasingly directive and costly (e.g., mandatory discounts during sales), heightening tension between online marketplaces and counterparties.

Fierce competition prevents marketplaces from limiting services solely to partners or their online storefronts. They provide a wide range of services for suppliers (warehouse and storage, courier delivery, marketing, call centers, etc.), including distribution, order processing, and logistics, which were previously offered only by specialized fulfillment operators. This increases dependence for smaller companies using the full suite of options, while larger suppliers maintain functional-market autonomy by selecting only a subset.

The expansion of services for sellers and the platform's audience strengthens its bargaining power relative to sellers, allowing it to raise fees and, consequently, increase marketplace profits.

Currently, this broad platform-seller interaction is poorly regulated by legislation, including due to ongoing discrepancies. For instance, Rospotrebnadzor "conceptually supports the goals of most bills", while representatives of the Ministry of Digital Development, Communications, and Mass Media of the Russian Federation consider that "regulating relations between marketplace owners, sellers, and buyers via a separate federal law is excessive" [39].

The scale of marketplace presence and the rapid growth of digital trade as a key sales channel demonstrate that regulating marketplaces requires stronger legislative consolidation of market practices to ensure platform development and fair interaction with partners.

It can be assumed a priori that such regulation should not be purely restrictive, as marketplaces are now essential institutional units of the commodity circulation sphere. Yet, their scale generates problems unsolvable by market forces alone.

Thus, the marketplace model, given the growing role of aggregators, demands more active development of the control and regulatory environment for online platforms [40], expanding market engagement, lengthening delivery chains, and facilitating access to foreign markets.

Further development of e-commerce necessitates expanded legislative initiatives and mechanisms to ensure fair market parity in platform-seller relationships, enhance consumer protection, and increase transparency in digital markets.

Legislative gaps in this field today hinder the development of marketplaces, whose corporate governance systems are evolving naturally but remain far from spontaneous.

Lack of an external regulatory framework necessitates greater efficiency and mitigation of reputational risks associated with interactions between sellers and buyers on the platform, particularly through compliance control mechanisms.

The main goal is to increase the legal and ethical standards for conducting and managing business processes in interactions with trading partners, which forms a foundation for sustainable ESG transformation of digital platforms.

This requires developing compliance procedures to reduce reputational risks for platforms and address asymmetries in market interactions with platform partners, considering the structure of paid service options and standard contractual terms.

The basic level of compliance for trading platforms should align with the requirements of the internal control system, which should be expanded through new regulations and local rules governing:

- 1) compliance with the fundamental consumer rights to exchange and return goods;
- 2) organization of effective oversight by platforms over suppliers and product assortments;
- 3) harmonization and establishment of balanced relationships with pick-up points and sellers.

The sustainable development of marketplaces should be elevated to a strategic priority for market growth and ESG transformation in this sector, with the modern market profile incorporating all relevant UN Sustainable Development Goals. At the same time, internal "calibration" at the management strategy level should account for key bottlenecks and structural asymmetries accumulated during platform development.

ESG-marking of the market activity profile of marketplaces should include a set of initiatives that contribute to more balanced trade cooperation with sellers and enhance the platform's reputational capital, including:

- ensuring the accuracy of product information and identifying the owners of pick-up points and sellers;
- increasing the transparency of information and interaction principles between buyers and marketplaces that are not direct parties to the transaction;
- creating an intuitive and flexible system for charging marketplace services, as well as rules for modifying fees (including storage, logistics, etc.);
- expanding platform accountability for the content presented and promoted, which will prevent the sale of counterfeit products and protect consumers' rights and interests [41];
- enhancing the organizational and methodological foundation of the internal compliance control system for marketplaces.

The effectiveness of a platform's compliance control system will be determined by the extent to which its economic policies, regulations, and internal documents are adjusted to define “new” working conditions, considering optimal and regulator-verified allocations of responsibility between the platform and the seller [42].

Improving the efficiency and sustainability of marketplace development should be based on a balanced approach that integrates internal compliance tools within corporate governance with antitrust compliance directed at external regulatory constraints.

DISCUSSION

In our view, the legislative framework for antimonopoly compliance remains weak, which increases reputational and financial risks for marketplaces despite progress in regulatory oversight in the Russian Federation. For example, practices such as forcing sellers to apply discounts or abruptly suspending sales from a distribution center and requiring them to remove their goods the same day do not formally violate existing regulations. However, they inflict significant reputational damage on the platforms and substantial financial losses on selling companies [42]. Although these actions do not breach the legally defined pricing procedures, they exacerbate existing imbalances in platform–seller relations and sharply increase the financial risks borne by counterparties.

The current legislative framework governing digital markets and the operation of large ecosystems therefore requires substantial refinement. Its structural gaps limit

the effectiveness of antitrust compliance and, because regulatory requirements remain minimal, create elevated risks for platforms in their interactions with sellers and end users. As a result, internal compliance mechanisms within marketplaces become increasingly important, as they help reduce risks associated with remote, digitally mediated retail interactions [43].

The development of effective compliance control tools in digital retail is complicated by the limited range of established practices and industry-specific cases in e-commerce. This is tied to the broad spectrum of digital supply chain management tools (e-SCM), automated partner interaction systems, customer-relationship management tools (e-CRM), and integration with warehouse, accounting, and enterprise management systems (ERP for large corporations) [44]. The absence of effective oversight of relationships between e-commerce participants (stemming above all from an underdeveloped regulatory framework) heightens financial risk, reputational vulnerabilities, and the potential erosion of corporate image [45].

Unlike internal control systems in traditional retail, which typically focus on areas such as cash-flow verification or inventory shrinkage, the control procedures applied in e-commerce are insufficient. European practice illustrates this: online abuse is increasingly prevented through specialized electronic algorithms that detect legal violations, and in international trade these mechanisms complement data-sharing systems used by national VAT administrations [46].

The organizational and technological complexity of marketplaces is reflected in their specialization and staffing needs. According to hh.ru job market data, the number of vacancies for managers of large platforms rose by 27% in 2023 and continues to grow [47]. To address these challenges, a dedicated structural unit for risk management and internal control should be established, following the example of major FMCG chains and in line with Article 258 of the Corporate Governance Code [48]. Minimizing personnel risks further requires the development of labor compliance – an internal system ensuring that employee functions align with labor law and platform regulations, and that labor disputes are resolved using legally established mechanisms (Article 1 of the Labor Code of the Russian Federation).

Introducing a compliance-based risk management system allows marketplaces to address acute personnel and security challenges at a time of rising demand for specialists and annual growth in the number of sellers, turnover, and orders, often by 50-60%. Implementing HR compliance controls, aligned with the distribution of functions across business processes, also reduces the risk of specialist shortages as

employee responsibilities increasingly include price and competitor analysis, supply management, SEO, marketing, and other areas.

CONCLUSION

In the context of platform-seller interactions examined above, the most urgent task today is to adjust the economic policies of marketplaces and build an internal compliance system aimed at preventing damage to their business reputation and minimizing the financial and reputational losses incurred by sellers. Restricting the scope of direct interaction between sellers and customers (an inherent feature of platform business models) further magnifies reputational risks and reduces profits for both sellers and marketplaces.

The contemporary ESG agenda for the development of commodity circulation, including its digital segment, underscores the importance of socially oriented business transformation. The growing market power of platforms must not generate disproportionate reputational risks, especially in terms of consumer benefits and convenience.

In practice, this will require marketplaces to substantially revise their business models, recalibrating how they interact with sellers and buyers to ensure more balanced and mutually beneficial relations. When this market parity is reflected in regulatory frameworks, external restrictions will support further improvements to legislation, enabling the sustainable growth of e-commerce and the strengthening of digital market competition. This, in turn, will heighten the effectiveness of antitrust compliance within the corporate governance systems of marketplaces.

The central message of this article is the need to balance internal compliance mechanisms, aligned with ESG-oriented strategies for sustainable transformation, with the core social (S) and corporate governance (G) components that ensure responsible and equitable platform development.

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INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Tatyana O. Grafova	Associate Professor, Dr. Sci. (Econ.), Professor of the Department of Economics, Accounting, and Analysis. Rostov State Transport University. Rostov-on-Don, Russia. E-mail: rubika78@mail.ru . ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4646-0155	Writing - Original Draft, Visualization
Yevgeniya A. Medvedkina	Associate Professor, Dr. Sci. (Econ.). Head of the Department of International Economics and Business. Don State Technical University. Rostov-on-Don, Russia. E-mail: emedvedkina@donstu.ru . ORCID: 0000-0002-4426-8020. Scopus Author ID: 57200082821	Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing
A. A. Vasil'tsov	Graduate student. Rostov State Transport University. Rostov-on-Don, Russia.	Writing - Review & Editing

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